

Towards an Urban Domesticity. Contemporary Architecture and the Blurring Boundaries between the House and the City

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ABSTRACT

The boundaries between domestic and urban environments are increasingly blurred. Until the contemporary era, the house acted as a quite autonomous microcosm and the city as its receptacle, but today this distinction is not so sharp. Various changes are transforming both domestic and urban life. Many activities, events and rituals usually associated with domestic space today take place often outside, scattering the home throughout the city. Meanwhile, domestic environment is increasingly accommodating some urban functions, changing its traditional meaning and giving rise to hybrid situations. Domestic and urban environments are merging in a symbiotic way; it is then necessary to rethink their spaces in order to respond to their contemporary and future evolutions. The paper aims at introducing the main facts about the contemporary blurring of the boundaries of domestic and urban space, explaining how this is currently affecting the architecture of both the house and the city.

Keywords: Domesticity; urban environment; urban lifestyle; gender; home

1. Introduction

Domestic and urban environments are apparently very different domains separated by spatial limits. House walls seem to draw a clear line of demarcation between them, unequivocally indicating where one realm begins and the other ends. However, this is true only when focusing on their physical boundaries: things get more complicated when attention is paid to their conceptual boundaries, that is, to those actions, events and situations that are usually associated with the urban or the domestic. Until the contemporary era, with its digital and gender revolution, the house was mostly perceived as a quite autonomous microcosm and the city as its receptacle, but today the distinction is not so sharp. Recent social, economic, political, technological and cultural changes have led to the emergence of new forms of living, that are rapidly transforming both domestic and urban life. Nowadays, many activities commonly related to domestic spaces often take place outside; at the same time, houses increasingly accommodate typically urban functions, giving rise to hybrid situations that modify the very idea of city and home.

Domesticity is more and more understood as a field, or as a mental territory that goes beyond the material, concrete spatial and bodily limits of the house (Chávez Giraldo 2010): it is a multidimensional domain, related to the intimate condition of human beings and their need for protection, care, rest, recovery and pleasure (Bachelard 2014; see also Mallett 2004). The identity of the space/home is constantly being redefined; it expands and contracts and increasingly depends not only on a specific physical interior, but also on a network of urban places. The paper aims to introduce this ongoing evolution, showing how changes in society, culture and economy are increasingly blurring the boundaries between domestic and urban environments. The discussion will focus on the current architectural and conceptual transformation of the idea of home. We argue that this transformation reflects, at least in part, emerging and mainly urban lifestyles. The paper does not pretend to produce brand-new definitions. Rather, its purpose is to highlight some contemporary processes which, although ambiguous and intangibles, are reshaping habits and places of a large part of the urban population.

These processes, and the changes they bring, are spreading very quickly, becoming an emerging global phenomenon. In order to analyse this phenomenon, the paper is divided into six parts: a section introducing the socio-cultural context of the contemporary blurring of boundaries between house and the city; four sections dealing with the transformations of the traditional domestic space of the main rooms (living room, bedroom, kitchen, bathroom); the conclusions. In each section, the paper discusses from different perspectives the ongoing changes in the understanding of the house and the city, and how those are affecting the architecture of domestic spaces. We consider that this layout can help to clarify a phenomenon otherwise difficult to describe, and at the same time facilitate the insertion of the selected case-studies. The paper does not claim that these transformations are occurring altogether, or that they will entirely replace the traditional relations between the domestic and the urban. It aims instead to discuss how

these phenomena are spatially changing the contemporary world, in order to better identify a shift that is becoming generalized.

2. Gender, Technology and Society

The gender revolution has significantly contributed to radically changing the concept of domesticity. From the 1960s onwards, many voices have denounced the traditional domestic environment as a space that did not allow the emancipation of women; an environment in which a great deal of unpaid work was required to maintain the suitability for restoring the productive capacities of workers (usually men) (Federici 2009). The unmasking of this “reproductive” function of the house (in the sense that it reproduces, regenerates, productive capacities) allows the woman to emancipate herself from the role of housewife, making possible the emergence of new forms of urban life that differ from the traditional family model (Brubaker 1993; Reigot and Spina 1996; Beck-Gernsheim 2003). In this radical transformation, the body acquires a new prominence. Freed from pre-constructed concepts, the body is identified as the starting point for constructing new social behaviours and a new meaning of domesticity, from new lifestyles based on a more heterogeneous and diversified structure (Madigan, Munro, and Smith 1990; Darke 1994; Gilroy and Woods 1994; Attfield and Kirkham 1989; Heynen and Baydar 2005; Taylor and Preston 2006).

New technologies are also playing a key role in the redefinition of domestic spaces and their relationship with the city. Contemporary media have already created new habits, which depend on patterns of life linked to the speed of action, the possibilities of individual devices and the expanded urban relationships (Giaccardi and Magatti 2001). All these phenomena have given rise to a different use of spaces, both urban and domestic; people actively interact with the environment through a digital layer, and this results in a totally new form of relationship with the city (La Cecla 1995). But the contemporary media are not only changing the way we relate to the domestic environment and to the outside world; they are also changing the way we relate to ourselves. Individuals increasingly have an existence that goes beyond their physical body; they also exist as bits of information (Sheller and Urry 2003). The diffusion of Internet, and with it of the new forms of instantaneous communication, has led to a kind of fragmentation of selves into different pieces scattered in virtual space. Nowadays, people can exist at the same time in the physical space, as moving bodies, and in the communicational space, wherever they left some of their information and identity: for example, in social networks, online gaming websites, or cross-platform messaging services. An important effect of this revolution is that the separation between house and the external world is becoming more and more thin. Today one can access the public world from his/her house, or communicate with people who live far away, or participate in real time of events happening in the farthest corners of the planet or enabling the domestic environment from a public place. Time, in contemporary era, is increasingly perceived as something that compresses or even

annihilates space (Rosa 2015). Personal life is now continuously invaded by distant events, relationship and experiences: through their electronic devices, individuals are constantly confronted with symbolic and cultural worlds that are completely outside their range of action, and that relate them to other domains even when these are not physically present; a timeless time (Castells 1996).

This abstraction goes both in the direction of a dematerialization of experience, and of its delocalization (Tomlinson 1999), in the sense that the physical context of the subject is no longer a constraint and can be easily bypassed. With the advent of broader, multi-level global connections and of virtual communities, the external world enters and permeates the domestic sphere, questioning the bourgeois meaning of home as a purely private place. The new contemporary media demand a continuous interaction with them, and this is already changing the uses and rituals associated with the different spaces of the house. It is increasingly common, for example, to transform the bedroom into a private living room, where one can connect with the outside and, at the same time, develop personal interests and individuality (Livingstone 2007). Similarly, the kitchen is turning into an individual workplace, the bathroom into a new social media office and the living room into an urban phenomenon (Martella 2018), as it will be better explained later in the essay. The once so clear boundary between inside and outside is fading. According to a marketing research conducted by IKEA in 2016, only 7% of respondents (250 families) identify a specific place as home. On the other hand, 37% believe that the concept of home extends outside the domestic walls; 38% identify home with the neighbourhood, while 18% identify it with the city itself (IKEA 2016). These data are a good example of the contemporary tendency to displace in the urban many activities, habits and affections traditionally linked to the domestic space, merging it with the city. Also, according to the same research, most people of the new generations – Millennials, Generation Z – feel more comfortable outside their houses, even for activities such as watching TV, relaxing or sleeping. At the same time, there is a reverse phenomenon: the habit, increasingly common among young people, of socializing from home, for instance through social networks, dating or messaging apps. Home, in the era of globalization, can be interpreted as an open and porous place, an intersection of social relations and emotions; its contemporary identity should be built on communication, movement, and interactions, able to enrich the daily life of individuals, more than on separation (Blunt and Dowling 2006). Another important aspect in the current evolution of the idea of home is the mobility of many urban inhabitants. In a sense, people have always been in constant motion, unless in exceptional situations where movement was restricted or conditioned. However, it seems possible to say that the contemporary citizens move faster and easier than ever before: from home to work (and backward), from one house to another, from one city to another, often from one country to another.

The twenty-first-century individual increasingly resembles the “the Derridian parasite” (Derrida 1988), the nomads of Deleuze and Guattari (1986), or Lyotard’s hobo (Lyotard 1993). The prototype of the contemporary individual is a mestizo with many identities

and multiple belongings, who chooses certain life patterns according to his/her values and beliefs; s/he is flexible, and able to adapt to the changing circumstances. More and more people today live in the condition that Verschaffel (2012) has defined “a-topia”, that is, as nomadic subject freed from the concept of belonging and in a state of perennial transit. With this new type of urban dweller, the perception of both domestic and urban space changes from permanent to temporary. Home, more than being associated to a stable and fixed place, may exist in many different locations and times, depending on where and when the body and the mind are in a specific moment (Chávez Giraldo 2010). The concept of home is increasingly merging with domains that were previously regarded as clearly separate, such as the working sphere. The possibility of being continuously connected, and the dissolution of the physical frontiers between interior and exterior, facilitate immaterial labour (Aureli and Giudici 2018). Depending on the job, today it is possible to contribute to the production system from any place; the domestic space is already one of its main cores. This is happening not only because new technologies make production ubiquitous, thus diminishing the importance of traditional work places (the office, for example); but also because immaterial production relies on aspects more typical of the domestic domain, such as sociability, affectivity, and care (Dogma 2015). This releases at the same time the latent productivity of the domestic space and the domesticity of the traditional workplace. Home could now be considered, for the first time in its recent history, a productive place, and the same goes for every place with an Internet connection: bars, trains, aeroplanes, banks, lawns, restaurants, cars, etc. (Mitchell 2004). In many fields, the separation between workplace and home is being erased, questioning the identity of the latter as a refuge from external worries and stress. This evolution of contemporary domesticity goes hand in hand with the changing notion of interior. Today, the domestic interior is often no longer understood as a finished product, but as a process in continuous evolution, which depends from the relationship between the house and the physical and emotional well-being of its inhabitants. Such relationship is able to generate an incredible variety of ways to inhabit domestic space (Attiwill 2012), and is supported and constantly remodelled on the basis of the flow of information produced by the current social system.

Precisely because one of its main influences comes from the outside, the domestic interior extends beyond the limits of the house and expands into the urban. The house tends to the city, and the city turns into a home; they share rooms, spaces, times and atmospheres. But changes in domesticity also arise from the evolution of the relationship between public and private domain, whose boundaries are increasingly mobile and fluid (Bauman 2000). Throughout the twentieth century, social sciences used to understand “public” and “private” as static and antithetical concepts: according to Sheller and Urry (2003) each “public” presuppose a certain contrasting “private”. Nevertheless, nowadays the distinction does not seem to be so clear. In many respects, “public” and “private” have already become complementary rather than antithetical moments of contemporary social life, overlapping and hybridizing their conceptual and physical boundaries (Sheller and

Urry 2003; see also Kumar and Ekaterina 2008). They now point to a multiplicity of different meanings, although often their semantic complexity is not fully recognized (Weintraub 1997). The blurring of traditional dualities (public/private, man/woman, work/leisure, inside/ outside, digital/material, nomad/sedentary) is giving rise to a new concept of domesticity, replacing the idea of the home as a closed space with fixed uses and a static identity: a concept that allows multiple meanings and that exists in a context that transcends physical boundaries, spreading around the global urban environment. A concept that, as Braidotti (2006) suggested, requires a reconfiguration of our being in the world, in the framework of a global and nomadic conception of the subject, that exists in a networked environment.

3. Living Rooms

The living room has so far played a central role in the hierarchy and identity of domestic spaces, and consequently also in their design. The 20th century living room is the merging of a series of spaces and functions that, in the bourgeois home, were spread across different rooms, such as the dining room, the lounge, the study or library, the fumoir and even the boudoir (Sustersic 2013). The modern living room was a multifunctional place, while all the other rooms were mostly associated with specific activities. The kitchen is the space where to cook; the bedroom is the space where to sleep; the bathroom is where one takes care of his/her own hygiene. In the living room, on the other hand, there are no particular limits to the activities that one can perform: it is, as the language clearly suggests, simply the space where to live. One can rest in living rooms, or socialize, or perform domestic rituals that symbolize the family union and strengthen ties with extended family and friends (Sennett 1977). The living room can be alternatively, and sometimes simultaneously, the private resting space of the inhabitants, and also where they relate to the outside, by receiving guests or turning on devices such as TV and radio that let the world in.

Because of its nature and openness towards the outside, the living room was the space more directly influenced by the ongoing social changes. It is no coincidence that it was the first and, for a long time, the only room in the house turned into an interactive multimedia centre incorporating the latest technological advances (Rechavi 2008). Contemporary shifts in economy, technology, society, city politics, and architectural thinking are bringing about new transformation in the living room and its domestic role. As a consequence of the greater possibilities of global communication and interaction, these changes are affecting many more aspects than in the past, also involving actively the urban context (Castells 1996). New media allow to escape from everyday life, transporting the users beyond the physical boundaries of architecture (Mitchell 2004). For this reason, the role of the living room as the only and exclusive place in the house where to interact with the outside, with the public realm, is gradually fading. Furthermore, the changes in the world of work and the advent of immaterial productions also have a

significant influence on the contemporary perception of the domestic. As the distinction between workplace and home becomes blurred, domestic spaces play an increasingly important role in the production system. Nowadays, some jobs may be carried out everywhere; some of them are better executed from a domestic space than from a traditional working environment (Colomina 2018). This is causing a gradual emptying of offices in major European cities, showing the rapid decline of the very typology of office space (Dogma 2015).

This phenomenon is directly related to the emergence of new jobs that require a particular organization of time and that dissolve the traditional distinction between leisure and work. The diffusion of new technologies, together with the introduction of the working sphere within the domestic environment, is already affecting the role of the living room in the house and consequently its spatial identity. Inside the domestic, the living room is being transformed. At the same time, spaces with the traditional meanings and architectural characteristic of living rooms are appearing in public or semi-public places, such as bars, hotels, airports, museums, offices, etc. Such places represent the new socialization hubs of a society based on maximizing performance and speed (Echeverría 1994); they allow the worker to rest in a context where the idea of traditional house no longer exists and where the housewife is freed from every domestic obligation (Amann Alcocer 2005), thus embodying the everyday life of the new global nomads (Deleuze and Guattari 1986) and materializing the Third Space of Bhabha (2004). Such places respond more directly and appropriately to a different idea of living in the porous space of the post-identity city, flexible, inclusive, augmented, open to continuous exchange and interaction between cultures.

The evolution of the living room as an urban phenomenon and its transformation inside the home can be appreciated in some trends already underway in major contemporary cities. One of these is the spread of co-housing and co-living arrangements, a typology of domestic environment where the traditional living room ceases to exist; in its place, a system of communal spaces with a marked public character is established, where the inhabitants can interact, forge relationships, build family-like connections. Such tendency can be observed in many of world's largest cities (Space 10 2017). In New York, co-housing company WeWork built in 2016 WeLive, a co-living residence intended to give young workers or to people who only have to pass a few months in the city a quite affordable place to stay (Wang 2016). Another example is Collective Old Oak, a co-living scheme built in London in 2016. Mainly targeted to young professionals aged between 21 and 35, at the moment of its construction it was the largest co-housing building in the world, being able to accommodate up to 550 people (Mairs 2016). But co-housing does not necessarily have to concern only students or young workers; the range of action of such typology is actually expanding, and today potentially affects the entire urban population (Studio Weave 2018). It was also in London where at the end of 2016 the first co-housing explicitly aimed at the elderly was built. Designed by Pollard Thomas Edwards for the Older Women's Co-Housing group, the project intended to provide a

space of socialization and sharing to a category of people at risk of suffering loneliness (Pollard Thomas Edwards 2017). But it is also possible to observe another trend that is somehow the other side of the coin of the latter. The living room is turning into a public phenomenon; many cities are equipping themselves with public and semi-public spaces that can serve as collective, open-air living rooms: intimate, domestic-like places to rest and relax inside the urban.

This phenomenon is immediately evident in the gentrification of bars that globally seek to provide an experience as much domestic as possible to their guests. Places such as Starbucks are configured as extensions of the house, with an appearance and use similar to those that traditionally had the living room (Watakanyaka, Zhara, and Atmodiwirio 2017). They are places where to converse, work, have fun, rest, meet friends, wrapped in the symbolic furniture, a system of objects (Baudrillard 1996), of the traditional living room, including sofas, tables, lamps, paintings; their aim is to allow the contemporary urban inhabitant, always without time and in continuous movement, to develop a personal experience of urban domesticity. The domestication of the urban environment may involve, for example, the design or rehabilitation of a vacant lot, such is the case of Campo de la Cebada, in Madrid. Campo de la Cebada is the name of an empty lot located in the heart of Madrid, which in recent years has undergone a process of recovery conducted by a collective of neighbours (El campo de la Cebada 2011). Through a few small operations, such as the design of temporary wooden furniture of different sizes, functions and formal complexity, the lot was actually transformed into a sort of collective living room, a place where the boundaries between domesticity and urbanity blurred. But similar results can also be achieved through the construction in the city spaces of microarchitectures that act as tiny public rooms open to everyone. This is the case for instance of the MINI Living urban cabins, a series of four temporary projects built between 2017 and 2018 in Los Angeles, New York, Beijing and London (Hobson 2018). Consisting each one of a pavilion of 15mq, urban cabins were intended to provide a place where one could enter to rest for a while, or read a book, or talk with some friends, and find a moment of peace in the bustle of the biggest cities.

4. Bedrooms

As the living room loses its traditional role as the central domestic space, the bedroom is turning into one of the main focus and directly reflects the personality of inhabitants (Livingstone 2007), taking the role of the living room as a multifunctional place. The bed and the sofa are slowly converging: in 2014 the bed overtook the sofa for the first time as the most used piece of furniture in British homes (Bose, Self, and Williams 2016). A bedroom culture is emerging, related to a generalized perception of the domestic environment as centre of cinematic entertainment and individual leisure, but also of work. In sociological terms, this reflects an underlying process of individualization, which highlights how traditional social distinctions (especially between social classes) are

diminishing in importance in the lives of new generations, and how they are being fragmented in a much wider context than the domestic one (Amann Alcocer 2005). In the modern house, the bed started to be understood not only as a place where to sleep or procreate, but also as an object opening to an entirely different form of industrialization and production. A new kind of factory without walls was constructed with compact electronics and extra pillows for the 24/7 generation (Colomina 2014), creating a new horizontal architecture that starts from the growing social role of the bed.

This “horizontal architecture” is magnified by the absence of hierarchies on the web and on social media, which are completely integrated into professional, business and industrial environments, and dissolve the traditional boundaries between public and private, work and leisure, rest and action (Matsuda 2010). Traditional home furnishings are progressively changing to meet the needs of the internet and social media generation, which is used to doing the most distinct actions in bed: millennials not only work in bed but also socialize in bed, read in bed, entertain sexual relationships in bed with people miles away (Colomina 2018). To address this evolution in the social role of bed, also its design is changing, in order to convert it into an element more suited to the new functions it is already playing in the lives of millennials.

Many contemporary designers are imagining the bed not so much as a neutral piece of furniture, but rather as a mini living room where various activities can be performed. An example of this is Flexit, a bed designed by Pieter Peulen for students dealing with a lack of space in their accommodations (Gibson 2017). Made up of two horizontal frames and a metal structure, the bed allows different configurations: it can become a bed with a desk next to it, or two beds next to each other, or a bunk bed; a series of clips also enable students to arrange a small wardrobe, a nightstand, a basket and a shelf. The same problem is approached by other designers through a different strategy, that is, the design of beds that is halfway between an object and a small room. Living Cube, by Till Könniker, is a very compact piece of furniture whose perimeter walls serve as shelves, wardrobe and desk, and whose interior can be used for storage or as a workspace (Meinhold 2014). Being modular, the various pieces of the Cube can also be arranged in different configurations. Following a similar approach, Yves Béhar together with MIT Media Lab designed ORI, a robotic system intended as a saving space solution (Fuseproject 2016). ORI is a furniture with a bed and a closet on one side, and the elements of a home office and a leisure suite on the other. The automated system allows the opening and closing of each of these elements at will, thus actually transforming a neutral space into a bedroom or living room. The increasingly indistinct boundary between workplace and home is also giving rise to a series of projects in which the bed becomes the key element of this hybridization. Some of these projects focus on the domestic space, thus, imagining beds for people having to work from home; others on the contrary focus on offices, designing sleeping pods or nap rooms where workers can take a time to rest. Grafeoiphobia: unexpected office, for instance, is a collection designed from Geoffrey Pascal explicitly for people used to working from the bed (Winston 2018). It consists of three slatted

wooden pieces designed to support the body in NASA's neutral body position, while at the same time allowing for several adaptations. The project aims both to provide practical furniture for people working at home, and to help transform common offices into more intimate and domestic work environments.

Less and less understood only as a place of rest, the bedroom is actually becoming a bridge between two environments previously understood as antithetical, such as home and workplace. The bed is turning into a multi-purpose object, capable at the same time of bringing a working atmosphere into the most private space of the house, and of bringing a sense of home into the offices. Many companies today use the bed to transform the overall atmosphere of their environments and make them more welcoming. Mattress brand Casper has furnished its offices in New York with sleeping pods, where workers can both take a nap or hold informal meetings. These sleeping pods are part of the more general project of the interiors of Casper's headquarters, designed by Float Studio. It is a project that per se says a lot about the hybridization between home and workplace, since all the common areas of the offices are designed to directly recall domestic spaces such as the kitchen, the dining room or the living room (Float studio 2017). This fusion of home and workplace aesthetics is a strategy that can be recognized in several contemporary projects. In New York, GRT architects have created an office for a UX design firm that similarly evokes the domestic atmosphere, both through the use of colours, materials and objects more likely to be associated with a domestic space, and through the creation of a nap room where workers can rest (GRT architects 2017). But the growing social importance of bed can also be appreciated in the diffusion of nap areas in the city; that is, not only in workplaces but also in public spaces, where the bedroom turns into an urban facility in which everyone can enter and sleep. This is the case, for example, of "Siesta & go" in Madrid, a bar that offers a place to sleep in the city centre; or of The Dreamery, a space built in New York in 2018 where people for a fee can enter and rest for 45 minutes. The bed, once the most intimate furniture of the house, is rapidly becoming the most directly linked to the urban and public environment.

5. Kitchens

In this context of change, the kitchen is also moving to the urban. In medieval towns, eating out was a common practice: few houses had kitchens, and people used to buy food from street vendors or send meals out to be cooked (Mennell 1985). In the Middle Ages, the kitchen was as much part of the urban environment as it was of the domestic, or even more (Sennett 1977). In modern times, however, the kitchen became central to domestic dynamics, as a new operating centre for the housewife in her task of regenerating her husband's productive capacities (Amann Alcocer 2005). The longer working hours and the ever-widening home/work distance, combined with the presence of a figure who is always present at home and devoted to household chores, have incredibly stimulated the culture of eating at home (Federici 1975). The kitchen, therefore, soon became the room that more than any other engineered all the operations necessary to maintain the illusion of domestic perfection (Puigjaner 2016). Only after the gender revolution and the

emancipation of women from domestic chores did eating out increasingly become important in the daily behaviours of the Western population. In fact, today, the choice of eating out can have different reasons. Sociability and conviviality are as much important aspects as work or lack of time.

What we eat has changed in the last decades, but above all, it also has changed the meaning of this activity. Feeding has long been the main concern in the struggle for survival of human beings; today, at least in some parts of the world, it is also a social fact linked to leisure, body care, social status and, in a minority of cases, even art (Steedmann 2017). In contemporary Western societies, eating out does not necessarily mean going to a restaurant. On the contrary, it is increasingly common to literally eat out, that is, in the space of the streets, after buying food in some fast-food chain or from some street vendor. This practice is now common among young people, hanging out for the pleasure of being together, but also among adults on break from work (Kumar and Ekaterina 2008); friendship and time savings are both good reasons enough to eat out. All of this is already leading to a shift in the way private behaviour in public streets is perceived (Valentine 1998). In Europe, 36.4% of the population eats outside on weekdays, a practice mainly related to employment and higher education. There are also workers and young people aged between 18 and 30 (Díaz Méndez, García Espejo, and Gutiérrez Palacios 2013) who do not eat at home during the week because of their working hours or because they live too far away.

Although they are a minority, there are also other reasons to eat out on weekdays, such as those related to leisure (20%), social relations (13%), comfort (4%) or simply not cook (3%) (Díaz Méndez, García Espejo, and Gutiérrez Palacios 2013). Domestic menus are not only offered by the refectories of companies, universities, schools, and hospitals, but also by establishments such as cafeterias, bars or restaurants; 22% of citizens use them also on weekdays, compared to 48.5% who do so on weekends. As a result, new ways of eating out appear, which take advantage of the contemporary situation and create new possibilities. These new ways include food tracks, apps to bring food anywhere in the city, urban kitchens, or also associations that cook for people who cannot or simply do not want to. But the ongoing evolution of the kitchen is due not only to the practice to eat out, but also to millennials' habit to order more and more food delivery. As a consequence of this, the market for prepared food is expanding, and a culture of tupperwares is developing (Steedmann 2017). According to the research "Is the kitchen dead?", conducted by UBS bank in 2018, millennials are three times more likely to order than their parents, and food delivery apps are constantly between the most downloaded app in major markets; this could lead, according to the study, to a 2030 scenario where most meals nowadays cooked at home are ordered and delivered (Cheng 2018). The future of domestic space, in this sense, could actually be that of a kitchenless house (Puigjaner 2016). And actually, kitchen and dining room have already started to migrate from domestic to urban environment. In the last years, for example, many cities saw the

diffusion of shared-use commercial kitchens, communal spaces that professionals of the food sector can use to cook and then deliver their products.

According to a report conducted by Ecosolutions together with the American Communities trust and Urban development, only in U.S. from 2013 to 2016 the number of such “kitchen incubators” increased by more than 50% to over 200 facilities (Wodka 2016). However, shared urban kitchens are currently not only targeted to food entrepreneurs. As small-space living become more and more frequent, in large cities are also appearing communal kitchens that everyone can rent to cook and celebrate events or simply spend some time with friends (Machtar, 2015). In 2019, Schemata architects built in Tokyo “kitchen studio SUIBA”, a sort of do-it-yourself restaurant where everyone can go and cook for themselves or other people, and then eat in the spaces of the restaurant itself (Schemata Architects 2019). The project aims both to provide a place to cook for people who do not have enough space in their homes but also to foster conviviality through the potential of food as a catalyst for social interactions. Cooking and eating together have always been actions capable of creating bonds, both by strengthening ties between members of the same social group, and by establishing new relationships between strangers.

It is no coincidence that many contemporary projects try to exploit the ability of food to bring people closer by giving a central role to kitchens and dining rooms. This strategy can be implemented for instance in co-living arrangements, such is the case of Teknobien, a student housing built by Murado Elvira in Trondheim in 2012. In this building, a large communal kitchen serves a major gathering device, being the space where the common life of the students is negotiated and where collective events and activities are mostly developed (Murado and Elvira 2012). But contemporary architecture sometimes uses the same strategy in more unusual and critical situations, where a sense of community has to be rebuilt. Some projects, aiming at fostering social relations, rely precisely on the design of urban kitchens, intended as places able to transform a group of people into a community. “Home for all” is the name of a program started by Toyo Ito in 2011 in response to Tohoku earthquake and tsunami. Ito, together with other architects, decided to build, in the post-disaster camps, some small civic centres where people could cook and eat together (Worrell 2013). In a situation where urbanity had been wiped out and domesticity reduced to the neutrality of temporary living pavilions, these shared kitchens became the only truly public spaces of the camps; at the same time, they also provided them a sense of the domesticity. They were, at the same time, the most urban and the most domestic place of the camps.

6. Bathroom

Today, gyms and sports centres act more and more as urban extensions of the domestic bathroom; they are intended at the same time as places where to socialize and meet other people, and as places where to continue that construction of a fit and clean body that starts right in the private bathroom. Many people, for instance, are now used to showering not

at home, but in the gyms once their training is over (Pardo Díaz 2016). Moreover, the city itself has already become in a sense a sort of open-air gym: the streets are increasingly full of runners of all ages, at all hours of the day; sports such as parkour, which basically consists in understanding urban space as the largest playground where to run and train, have had in recent years a remarkable spread. In contemporary Western societies, body care is not just about health or well-being; it is increasingly a way to manifest a certain social status. While once, to show power and status, it was enough to surround oneself with “nice things”, today people are progressively striving to be themselves “a nice thing” and thus embody their social position (Carolan 2005).

This obsession with the perfect body in many cases goes hand in hand with the idea of perfect cleanliness. The new social standards of personal and domestic hygiene, resulting from the sanitary reforms of the modern era, go far beyond the sheer necessity (Hancock et al. 2000). The need for the cleanest body and the cleanest house is a side effect of the culture of consumption, which presents both the human and architectural body as potentially endlessly and regenerable products. Neither the body nor the house, the consumption culture seems to suggest, are products of planned obsolescence; taking care of them is to give them an endless life (Pardo Díaz 2016). In this context, the bathroom is the space equipped for body care rituals. It is a laboratory where the construction of the public image takes place, the one that most corresponds to the standards dictated by society. At the same time, it is also where to fight against the signs of age, which say that the body indeed is a product of planned obsolescence, like or not.

The bathroom, somehow, is becoming the place where one struggles to defeat time (Alftberg and Hansson 2012). As body care is becoming more and more important in western societies, transcending the hygienic aspect to become a distinctive cultural feature, increasingly refined products are making their appearance in the domestic space. Objects that were once only used by professionals are now available to everyone. The typical items of the bathrooms of only a few years ago are being replaced by their professional versions: in today’s houses, it is not uncommon to find electric toothbrushes once used only by dentists, hair curlers able to properly do the work of a hairdresser, laser epilators that would fit in the best beauty salons, or razors and shaving products that were once prerogative of barbers only. Also, several ads insist on the possibility of buying these products and become an expert in body care at your place (Pardo Díaz 2016). In this way, the bathroom gains a whole new dimension, which goes beyond its traditional function of space where to look after one’s own hygiene.

In a way, the bathroom is becoming a synthesis of all those urban establishments and venues dedicated to body care; a domestic, private spa one can enjoy in his/ her own home. Similarly, the bathroom maintains the same private atmosphere it always had, but paradoxically also opens to the outside. In fact, also the bathroom could participate to immaterial production while, at the same time, is becoming the preferred place for digital voyeurism (Jaque, 2017). New technologies, together with the increasing importance of body care, are transforming it into a space charged with erotic implications. Many of the

pictures and video used for dating apps and sexting are taken in the bathrooms; this happens because the other rooms are increasingly perceived as public for such actions (Aggleton et al. 2018). The bathroom often becomes a background element of the new digital sexuality; its aesthetic is becoming increasingly important in this kind of communication. It is a space with a certain public exposure, and that therefore should appear welcoming and pleasant. For the same reason, it should also reflect the personalities and passions of the owners: a (digitally) public space.

Several contemporary projects, trying to imagine the possible future configurations of the bathroom, conceive it precisely as the most comfortable and relaxing space in the house: an environment where to regenerate and revitalize not only the body but also the mind. This does not necessarily imply the design of large, luxurious spaces. In 2018, Sieger Design created a six square metre home spa for micro-apartments, intended to respond to shrinking apartment sizes (Morris 2018). As life in small dwellings is becoming increasingly common in larger cities, the project aimed to find a way to provide even the tiniest houses with a space where people can relax properly. However, also in the case of the bathroom, it is the new multimedia that are mainly pushing its transformations. In recent years, many researchers and companies have begun to focus on the production of “smart bathrooms”, fully equipped with the latest technology. In a bathroom prototype designed by FutureHaus, a research program of the Virginia Tech Centre, technology regulates water heat and light energy, reduces energy consumption, provides the most diverse information through an interactive mirror, and calibrates all the elements of space to provide the users the best experience (FutureHaus 2016). In a smart bathroom, technology somehow takes care of users. But the integration of technology in the bathroom not only aims to make it more comfortable and hygienic; it also aims to make it safer for the elderly and disabled to use. At the same time, smart bathrooms could also safeguard the health of users through the analysis of their waste (Jaglarz 2018).

7. Conclusions

Socio-economic changes, together with the spread of digital technologies, are transforming our lives at an unprecedented rate. Urban and domestic environments are equally affected by these transformations; new habits and social behaviours are emerging that directly influence our experience of both home and the city. Domesticity is evolving, expanding more and more in the urban field, and thus gaining complexity. Nowadays, for many people home is not so much a stable and fixed place enclosed within four walls, but a series of interconnected fragments scattered throughout the city. With the evolution of domesticity, also urbanity is changing, as more and more of its functions and activities are integrated in this new-extended domestic environment. Many of the dualities traditionally used to interpret the inhabited landscape are rapidly blurring: not only urban and domestic but also public and private, inside and outside (Echeverría 1995), intimate and shared. Public sphere blends with the private and vice versa; inside and outside are categories constantly blurred by new media; intimate and shared are converting into complementary rather than contradictory concepts; urban and domestic are quickly

becoming the same domain seen from different points of view. More than a refuge from the outside world, home is turning into a point of observation of a global landscape where topology and ideology are mutually implied in the construction of a new concept of domesticity: a mental, rather than a spatial construction (Bachelard 2014). All the traditional rooms of the house are evolving and changing their original meanings; the way they are used and understood is changing, and consequently also their role in the overall experience of domesticity.

Until now, emerging lifestyles had to find their place in the context of the traditional domestic environment. However, new uses are appearing that demand spaces with very specific characteristics. These uses cannot always be properly accommodated in the domestic environment as it is currently understood. This is where the need for a farsighted vision of the future spatiality of the home becomes more evident. For example, home is becoming one of the preferred places for immaterial production; the coexistence between its old structure and these new needs becomes increasingly complicated as the latter gain importance. Flexible rooms are no longer enough to deal with this transformation. There is an increasing need for an adequate space in which to place the necessary equipment and devices; a space in which production activity can take place without constantly intertwining with domestic life. Similarly, the kitchen could experience an important evolution, becoming a less frequently used space, even more integrated with the living room. In the future, the kitchen is likely to be downsized in favour of other spaces. Today the dimension of the kitchen still responds to the needs of a traditional family, although in urban contexts only 40% of the population can be defined as family (Eurostat 2013). The remaining 60%, that is, students, young workers, couples, elderly, are forced to live in domestic environments designed for other contexts and other needs. Bedroom is also likely to evolve according to their new public role. For example, they could be reconfigured to accommodate different functions throughout the day. Contemporary bedrooms are increasingly connected with the digital layer and its devices. A bedroom designed to meet its new role within the domestic would be more ergonomic, facilitating the assumption of different positions according to the activities carried out. The bathroom itself could undergo significant changes, regarding both its tendency towards professionalization and its increasingly voyeuristic character. What is not anymore taking place inside the home (actions, rituals, events, places, atmospheres, affections) is now increasingly absorbed by the city, whose offer is addressed to all users regardless of their condition, age, race and gender: a better environment for the contemporary nomad (Deleuze and Guattari 1986). The traditional idea of home used to be associated with intimacy. Today, however, new forms of intimacy are emerging, linked not so much to a physical place but rather to a series of conditions that can occur everywhere, as long as a Wi-Fi connection is available.

This evolution is likely to continue in the future, leading to even more changes in the way we conceive domestic and urban environments. Throughout history, domestic architecture has changed over and over again to adapt to social transformations (Self 2016); similarly,

its relationship with urban space has also changed. The ongoing changes are of such importance that it seems necessary to start rethinking the domestic space, in order to be able to properly respond to those future questions that the present already allows us to glimpse. Home is migrating to the city, while the city is becoming domestic in all its aspects and in all its spaces.

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